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San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

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DEVELOPMENT AND ACCEPTABILITY OF ALERTO: A LOCALIZED DRRM LEARNING MODULE

**AMOR C. HABILING
POLICARPIO A. HABILING**

Pililla National High School
SDO Rizal Region 4A CALABARZON

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to develop and evaluate localized disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) learning modules. The researchers involved DRRM coordinators and senior high school teachers to assess the acceptability of the learning module based on content validity, relevance, clarity, and applicability. The results showed high acceptability among respondents, and the study recommends its use in DRRM training.

INTRODUCTION

Schools, as a crucial part of the community, are prone to disasters and emergencies that can disrupt education and put students and the entire learning community at risk. Republic Act No. 10121, recognizes the vital roles of schools in promoting awareness to prevent and mitigate disasters, thus requiring educational institutions to develop and implement disaster risk reduction and management plans. The strong conviction of this directive ensures that DRRM programs in schools can significantly reduce the impact of disasters and prevent the loss of lives and property.

However, the insufficient information education and communication (IEC) and localized learning materials intended to promote disaster awareness, preparedness, prevention, and mitigation at the school level are challenging.

This action research study aimed to develop and evaluate localized disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) learning modules for school-based training programs.

METHODOLOGY

The development of ALERTO, a localized DRRM learning module was guided by the ADDIE model, which is a known educational framework for producing effective learning materials. The module has five parts that focus on the common disasters in the Philippines and was written in Tagalog. The study employed both developmental and descriptive research designs. A teacher-made survey

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questionnaire, validated by experts, was used as the data-gathering technique. The study involves DRRM coordinators and senior high school teachers teaching DRRM subjects, who were chosen purposively and are responsible for assessing the acceptability of the learning materials based on content validity, relevance, clarity, and applicability. In addition, the researchers also utilized the LRMSD Evaluation and Review Criteria for printed material to determine the alignment of the localized learning material to the standard of the Department of Education. Weighted mean and independent t-tests as statistical tools were used to analyze the data and draw conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results show that the level of acceptability of the localized DRRM learning module for the four criteria as perceived by the DRRM coordinators is reflected in an average weighted mean of 4.54, which translates to a 'Highly Acceptable' rating. Similarly, the SHS DRRM teachers gave an average rating of 4.61, also indicating a 'Highly Acceptable' result. This data highlights the high level of acceptability of the learning modules among the respondents. This implies that both groups view the localized DRRM learning modules as acceptable in a comparable way.

The study recommends the use and implementation of these materials in the DRRM training workshop for students and teachers, as well as the regular monitoring and evaluation of their effectiveness and relevance to the needs of the community.

Keywords: Evaluation, localized, module

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